

Dear Reader,

It is with mixed feelings that we present the final newsletter of the ySKILLS project, a culmination of years of dedicated research and exploration into the dynamic world of digital literacy among youth. Our journey was significant as we sought to comprehend the complex aspects of digital literacy and how it affects the lives of young people in the digital era.

Leen d'Haenens
Coordinator, on behalf of the ySKILLS team

YSKILLS FINAL CONFERENCE

The ySKILLS Final Conference was held at the Irish College in Leuven, on November 30th, with the theme "Are children adequately prepared for the digital world?"

The conference drew an audience of over 200 people on the day when research results were presented and debated. For more information and conference videos, please go to the [ySKILLS Final Conference Interactive Report](#).

Photos by Willem Joris and Rita Baptista.

ALIGNING RESEARCH AND POLICY

EVIDENCE-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

Built on evidence developed during the research, the recommendations are directed to:

- EU and PAN-European legislators and policymakers;
- National policymakers;
- Educational authorities.

Evidence-based recommendations for policy and practice
Multimedia report

“In a world that is inherently digital, our goal is not to isolate children from mobile phones, but rather to empower them with essential literacy skills to navigate this digital landscape with intelligence and responsibility. Let us primarily advocate for evidence-based policies and reject policies that lack a foundation in research.”

(From the final Conference panel)

To read the recommendations check out the full report [“Children and young people \(aged 12-17\)’s digital skills: Evidence-based recommendations for policy and practice”](#) and the [Multimedia report](#).

TURNING ySKILLS RECOMMENDATIONS INTO ACTION POINTS FOR EU POLICY

Is the European Union (EU) current policy adequate to promote youth's digital skills and wellbeing in the digital environment?

Which actions are suggested by the evidence to improve the digital skills of European children?

In the [full report](#), we offer EU policymakers key action points on how to best ensure and promote children's digital skills based on ySKILLS results. A summary is also available [here](#).

Is the current policy at the level of the European Union (EU) adequate to promote youth's digital skills and wellbeing in the digital environment? Which actions does the evidence suggest to improve the digital skills of European children?

The ySKILLS project created **action points** to reveal the areas where EU policy can work to **improve children's digital skills**. These are organised into four themes: **Conceptualisation, Measurement and Research, Public, Regulatory and Communication and Stakeholders**.

Notes: The action points are listed per theme.

CONCEPTUALISATION, MEASUREMENT AND RESEARCH

1. Invest in structural, longitudinal and cross EU research which implements the ySKILLS Youth Digital Skills Index to measure the different dimensions of children's digital skills over an extended period and across various geographical locations.
2. Invest in the future development and fine-tuning of the ySKILLS, especially in light of new technological developments which may impact the dimensions of digital skills.

Summary of action points [website](#).

NEW POLICY BRIEF

The last Policy Brief demonstrates how ySKILLS translates evidence into actionable policy recommendations for EU policymakers. These recommendations include: Appointing a Digital Skills Coordinator; Prioritising diversity-centric policies; Fostering collaboration between the EU and Member States in digital education; Monitoring regulatory impact; Engaging stakeholders; Investing in research.

The “Policy Brief 4: The ySKILLS Research Network: Charting Pathways to Digital Youth Wellbeing” is available [here](#).

ALIGNING RESEARCH WITH RESOURCES

The ySKILLS resources have been developed based on the research tools, findings, and recommendations of the project. They are intended to help individuals gain insight into the digital challenges faced by children and young people, as well as to offer tools for enhancing their digital skills.

The resources are divided into sections: **Recommendations & interactive reports; Animation; Toolkits**. Here you find some of these resources. Check out all the resources on the ySKILLS website [here](#).

RECOMMENDATIONS

MENTAL HEALTH AND DIGITAL SKILLS

Research has demonstrated that young people frequently experience a lack of support when navigating the digital world, which can result in challenges in managing their online lives.

To assist both **young people** and **child support professionals** in addressing these issues, we offer recommendations for each group, in ten languages, [here](#).

DIGITAL CHALLENGES AND SKILLS OF REFUGEE TEENS IN EUROPE

Digital technologies offer both risks and opportunities to young refugees living at Europe's margins. To assist stakeholders actively involved in enhancing their wellbeing, education, and protection by addressing these issues, we offer recommendations [here](#). Available in English, Greek and Persian.

1. دسترسی به فناوری

- اطمینان حاصل کنید که منابع مالی و برنامه های قابل اجرایی برای حمایت از دسترسی منظم پناهندگان به فناوری، که اکنون برای مشارکت فعال در آموزش، زندگی اجتماعی و خانوادگی ضروری است، وجود دارد. اینها شامل گزینی های هوشمند، اتصال اینترنتی قابل اعتماد و رایانه می شود.

- منابع دسترسی مانند سیمکارت ها و طرح های داده گران قیمت و همچنین سخت افزار های غیر مقرون به صرفه مانند رایانه ها را برطرف کنید. جوانان برای توسعه مهارت های دیجیتالی پیشرفته نیاز به دسترسی به طیف وسیعی از زیرساخت ها دارند.

- با مقامات محلی، مدارس، و سازمان های غیر دولتی برای تامین دسترسی به زیرساخت های مقرون به صرفه یا رایانه ای برای پناهندگان همکاری کنید.

Here is an example of a recommendation to policy makers, in Persian.

INTERACTIVE REPORT

The interactive report on **Digital Skills and Literacy for Children's Rights** identifies the evidence on children's digital skills, and maps it to 11 child rights principles. Available [here](#), it is designed to support policymakers, researchers, child practitioners and advocacy and child rights activists to implement children's rights in a digital world.

Please refer to the blog post: "[Respect, protect, fulfil: how digital literacy enables the realisation of children's rights](#)" and the full report [here](#), to know more.

ALIGNING RESEARCH WITH RESOURCES

ANIMATION

The animation **Children's Rights in a Digital World** shows:

- How each one and the society can help kids navigate the world of apps, websites, games and social media;
- What issues should developers of digital products and spaces consider when they are designing for young audiences?

This animation is available [here](#) in Dutch, English, Estonian, French, Polish and Portuguese.

TOOLKITS

EDUCATION TOOLKIT

This Education Toolkit explores various digital skills targeting adolescents aged 12-17. It consists of two modules, 'Evaluate' and 'Execute,' with each model offering self-contained activities that can be conducted with breaks in between.

EVALUATE

Digital uses, needs, responsibilities, skills & knowledge

EXECUTE

Information browsing and searching, content production, communication & interaction

This website includes complete session plans and downloadable PDF materials for facilitating the activities. The six activities are designed to be versatile and can be employed by both educators and individuals in informal settings. Available in English, Estonian, Italian, and Portuguese [here](#).

MORE RESOURCES, RESULTS, AND NEWS

RESOURCES

All ySKILLS resources are available [here](#).

PUBLICATIONS

ySKILLS reports and other materials are available [here](#).

YSKILLS BLOG POSTS

- Interpersonal and commercial dimensions of privacy literacy: new findings from ySKILLS;
 - The Significance of Tailored Media and Digital Education Programmes for Refugee Children.
- All posts [here](#).